

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) shelx

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: shelx

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0014 A Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=7.7907(3) b=8.8430(3) c=18.2505(8)
 alpha=90 beta=96.454(4) gamma=90

Temperature: 150 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1249.37(8)	1249.37(8)
Space group	P 21/n	P 21/n
Hall group	-P 2yn	-P 2yn
Moiety formula	C16 H30 N6 O2, 2(F6 P)	?
Sum formula	C16 H30 F12 N6 O2 P2	C16 H30 F12 N6 O2 P2
Mr	628.40	628.40
Dx,g cm-3	1.670	1.670
Z	2	2
Mu (mm-1)	0.292	0.292
F000	644.0	644.0
F000'	644.93	
h,k,lmax	13,15,31	13,15,31
Nref	6685	6350
Tmin,Tmax	0.966,0.971	0.780,1.000
Tmin'	0.943	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.780 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.950 Theta(max)= 37.726

R(reflections)= 0.0410(4687) wR2(reflections)= 0.1161(6350)

S = 1.039 Npar= 231

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format
test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.
Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

PLAT244_ALERT_4_C Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of P Check

Alert level G

PLAT231_ALERT_4_G Hirshfeld Test (Solvent) P --F5A . 5.4 s.u.
PLAT302_ALERT_4_G Anion/Solvent/Minor-Residue Disorder (Resd 2) 86% Note
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O1 108.5 Degree
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G Short Inter X...Y Contact F1B ..C1 2.92 Ang.
x,-1+y,z = 1_545 Check
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G Short Inter X...Y Contact F5A ..C7 2.95 Ang.
3/2-x,-1/2+y,1/2-z = 2_645 Check
PLAT779_ALERT_4_G Suspect or Irrelevant (Bond) Angle in CIF # 20 Check
F1A -P -F1B 1.555 1.555 1.555 8.50 Deg.
PLAT779_ALERT_4_G Suspect or Irrelevant (Bond) Angle in CIF # 27 Check
F3A -P -F3B 1.555 1.555 1.555 4.30 Deg.
PLAT779_ALERT_4_G Suspect or Irrelevant (Bond) Angle in CIF # 31 Check
F6A -P -F6B 1.555 1.555 1.555 5.00 Deg.
PLAT779_ALERT_4_G Suspect or Irrelevant (Bond) Angle in CIF # 38 Check
F2A -P -F2B 1.555 1.555 1.555 9.90 Deg.
PLAT779_ALERT_4_G Suspect or Irrelevant (Bond) Angle in CIF # 49 Check
F4A -P -F4B 1.555 1.555 1.555 5.60 Deg.
PLAT779_ALERT_4_G Suspect or Irrelevant (Bond) Angle in CIF # 56 Check
F5B -P -F5A 1.555 1.555 1.555 1.60 Deg.
PLAT811_ALERT_5_G No ADDSYM Analysis: Too Many Excluded Atoms ! Info
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min). 3 Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 331 Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 5 Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain

0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully

1 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight

15 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data

4 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient

1 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low

10 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion

1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

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